

D4.1 - Guidelines on planned actions for recruitment and retention

WP4 -Balancing recruitment, retention and career progression

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MINDtheGEPs
gender equality in research

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Information in this report that may influence other MINDtheGEPs tasks

Linked task	Suggested recommendations
T4.1 Supporting women in their careers	<p><u>Action 1</u>: Needs analysis in the area of gender empowerment in research</p> <p>Recommendation 1: Collect existing data.</p> <p>Recommendation 2: Assessments of needs at the individual level should recognize participants' knowledge, skills and attitudes towards gender issues as well as their disempowerment risk</p> <p>Recommendation 3: Assessment of needs at the institutional level should be recognized on the basis of the gathered data about gender inequalities in your institution.</p> <p><u>Action 2</u>: Preparation of training</p> <p>Recommendation 1: Ensure standards by choosing adequate methodology.</p> <p>Recommendation 2: Ensure standards by preparing high quality content and materials.</p> <p>Recommendation 3: Ensure a high standard by choosing a suitable expert trainer</p> <p><u>Action 3</u>: Promotion and recruitment of the training</p> <p>Recommendation 1: Leadership Commitment</p> <p>Recommendation 2: Communicate training to key agents</p> <p>Recommendation 3: Consider Obligatory Training</p>

	<p>Recommendation 4: Engaging Men as Gender Equity Allies</p> <p><u>Action 4</u>: Conducting the training</p> <p>Recommendation 1: Verify if the workshop activities cover the following issues in all three areas of the workshop interest</p> <p><u>Action 5</u>: Training evaluation including both trainers and trainees' input</p> <p>Recommendation 1: A standard section (1-2 questions) in course evaluation to confirm gender sensitivity of the course should be prepared by the institution.</p> <p>Recommendation 2: If possible, orchestrate a follow up with participants, for example networking event, lean in circles, zoom calls etc.</p>
<p>T4.2 Supporting caregivers in their careers</p>	<p><u>Action 1</u>: Setting up a webpage dedicated to work-family balance</p> <p>Checklist</p> <p><u>Action 2</u>: Negotiation with the leadership for work-life balance measures</p> <p>Recommendation 1. Know the issue.</p> <p>Recommendation 2 Articulate the gains (and harms).</p> <p>Recommendation 3. Connect the advocated measures to the organisational, national and/or international legal provisions and policies.</p> <p>Recommendation 4. Clarify your aim.</p> <p>Recommendation 5. Build alliances.</p> <p>Recommendation 6. Communicate effectively.</p> <p>Recommendation 7. Embed measures.</p> <p>Recommendation 8. Monitor implementation of measures.</p>
<p>T4.3 Increasing gender awareness and breaking down stereotypes at the top</p>	<p><u>Action 1</u>: Needs analysis in the area of breaking down gender stereotypes in research and academia</p> <p>Recommendation 1 Define the goals of the training</p> <p>Recommendation 2 Identify expected change achieved by the training</p> <p>Recommendation 3 Identify the areas where the action is most needed</p> <p>Recommendation 4. Identify processes and procedures which support the foreseen change</p>

	<p>Recommendation 5 Identify potential organizational challenges and resistance among staff</p> <p><u>Action 2:</u> Preparation of training (for woman and men in top management positions)</p> <p>Recommendation 1 Ensure standards by choosing adequate methodology</p> <p>Recommendation 2 Ensure standards by preparing high quality content and materials</p> <p>Recommendation 3 Ensure standards by choosing professional equality trainer.</p> <p><u>Action 4:</u> Conducting the training</p> <p>Recommendation 1 Make sure that the workshop - checklist</p> <p><u>Action 5:</u> Training evaluation including both trainers and trainees' input</p> <p>Recommendation 1 Verify, accordingly to the set objectives, if a desired outcomes had been achieved.</p> <p>Recommendation 2 Compare trainers' and trainees' perspectives.</p>
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1. Introduction: MINDtheGEPs project

The European project MINDtheGEPs (Modifying Institutions by Developing Gender Equality Plans) takes a multidisciplinary multidimensional approach to challenge gender imbalances across five different countries with traditional gender regimes (Italy, Spain, Serbia, Ireland, Poland) and across various types of RPOs: 4 public universities (Turin, Tralee, Gdansk, Jagiellonian) and 1 public non-academic research institute (CNR); 1 academic (Belgrade) and 1 private technological institute centre (Galicia). The consortium, led by the University of Turin's CIRSDe, comprises also of three non-implementing organisations bringing complementary expertise in monitoring and evaluation (Knowledge and Innovation), research communication (Uppsala University) and scientific publishing (Elsevier). In order to promote systemic institutional change and following the "no data-no policy" principle, the project will map the existing data and, building on the tools developed within an ongoing research project of the project coordinator, will produce new qualitative-quantitative evidence. On this basis, both structural and cultural actions can be effectively designed. At a cultural level, the project will organise a virtuous chain of training, starting from across-partners "train the trainers" workshops to within-partners laboratories addressed to young women, but endorsing the approach of "fixing the system not the women", also to men and senior researchers. At structural level, the project will introduce work-family measures addressed also to men, equality targets in decision-making boards and gender-sensitive research. The establishment of proper figures and bodies creates conditions for the endurance of GEPs beyond the project's life. A multidisciplinary team (also including key-persons in middle or top management), coupled with a multi-skilled Advisory Board (including relevant national authorities), and 4 professional associations both in STEM and SSH, will contribute to a successful change in RPOs and in society at large.

1.1 Introduction and objectives of the deliverable

The overall objectives of deliverable 4.1 are:

Implementing policy actions to raise awareness at both the bottom and the top of gendered organizational practices in recruitment, retention and career progression;

Supporting scientific research excellence by searching for and hiring the best candidates without the effect of unconscious gender bias;

Supporting women researchers in the development of their careers;

Fostering dialogue, relevant cooperation and professional exchange among recruitment-promotion teams;

Facilitating the uptake of gender equal practices in the implementing institutions, through internal and external dissemination;

Favouring self-reflexivity through participative evaluation efforts

In this deliverable, which is based on a combination of desk research, our own expertise, MTG partners' experiences, in addition to existing guidelines, we have prepared a set of overall recommendations supporting academic and non-academic organizations to foster the awareness of gender issues in the field of recruitment, retention and career progression. Our guidelines on planned actions are developed to help to understand and prepare organisational change, which should improve gender equality in an institution.

2. Methodology

To facilitate the work of trainers and academics and offer good recommendations in training across academia (including gender equality issues) and in advocating for gender balanced solutions in the field of recruitment, retention and career progression, it is important to follow certain actions which would support organisational change in the context of diversity and inclusion paradigms.

The way we have collected this information has been through five different sources:

1. Indications taken from previous tasks carried out within the framework of the MINDtheGEPs project itself, such as indications arising from the state-of-the-art review in T2.1 “State of the art review” or the narratives given in T2.6 “Qualitative analysis: interviews with male and female researchers at different grades, across all dimensions” among others.
2. Inputs from other projects oriented towards gender equality (such as GE Academy, GEA-Gendering academia, R&I PEERS, CALIPER, FESTA, GENERA, etc.)
3. Experience and existing actions from consortium partners. The MINDtheGEPs consortium consists of 10 different partners, each of them with a different form of organisation and with different initiatives implemented that can serve as feedback within the consortium itself to obtain ideas of good practices.
4. Additional materials provided by desk research, not only related to EU Gender Equality projects, but any organisation that has been able to add value in some way in aspects related to gender equality.
5. Lessons learned through MINDtheGEPs workshops and activities. For example, at the “Train the trainers”, a two-day training workshop to build capacity for sustainable change in partner organisations. Between 7-8 June, around 50 people met in Vigo (Spain) to discuss basic concepts and tools to promote organisational change, and how situated knowledge can support the implementation of gender equality plans.

The combination of all these tools served as indications to follow in order to develop the core of this deliverable, ***Guidelines on planned actions for recruitment and retention*** for research organisations (academic and non-academic).

3. Recommendations for empowering women in their careers

Action 1	Needs analysis in the area of gender empowerment in research and academia
Action 2	Preparation of training composed of the modules: (1) Supporting Skills Development; (2) Deconstructing Unconscious Gender Biases; (3) Becoming a leader
Action 3	Promotion and recruitment of the training
Action 4	Conducting the training
Action 5	Training evaluation including both trainers and trainees' input

3.1 Action 1: **Needs analysis in the area of gender empowerment in research**

Recommendation 1: Collect existing data on the intersections of gender inequalities in your institution and make informed choice of the particular groups that should be trained.

Recommendation 2: Assessments of needs at the individual level should recognize participants' knowledge, skills and attitudes towards gender issues as well as their disempowerment risk (e.g. barriers and difficulties they experience in their academic careers). Make sure that you ask about the needs in all three areas (supporting skills development, deconstructing unconscious biases, becoming a leader)

Recommendation 3: Assessment of needs at the institutional level should be recognized on the basis of the gathered data about gender inequalities in your institution (e.g. databases, reports and studies prepared during the MDG project, your institution's GEP etc.)

3.2 Action 2: **Preparation of training composed of the modules: (1) Supporting Skills Development; (2) Deconstructing Unconscious Gender Biases; (3) Becoming a leader**

Recommendation 1: Ensure standards by choosing adequate methodology that take into account the institutional context and the assessment of participants' needs. Different techniques could include lotus blossom, storyboards, cultural web exercises (e.g. ACT Co-Creation Toolkit 2021; National Women's Council of Ireland,2014; SUPERA Webinar on Unconscious bias: <https://www.superaproject.eu/event/webinar-4/>). SUPERA Webpage on Tools and Techniques: <https://www.superaproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/Lotus-Blossom.pdf>

Recommendation 2: Ensure standards by preparing high quality content and materials.

Please make sure that you include all three areas of workshop interests (supporting skills development, deconstructing unconscious gender biases and becoming a leader).

Recommendation 3: Ensure a high standard by choosing a suitable expert trainer, for example a professional EDI/DEI trainer. It is imperative that the style, values, and beliefs of the trainer from a gender equality perspective are aligned with the goals of your organisation.

3.3 Action 3: **Promotion and recruitment of the training**

Recommendation 1: Leadership Commitment – Ensure commitment/ motivation/ accountability from key stakeholders. It is advisable to get good buy in from the start for the need for this training. There needs to be understanding and support from top-management.

- Require senior, middle and line managers to endorse and encourage staff to attend the training.
- Encompass a pre-work discussion with line managers/HOD to ensure they're aware of the training and the benefits in which it entails.
- Ensure training is supported by career development/research office and HR department. Expand the organisation's transformational agent network by involving different actors and departments.

Recommendation 2: Communicate training to key agents

- Open Expressions of Interest on organisation's public website and email network.
- Develop a tailored logo representing the gender equality training. This can be used to promote the training on various posters, documents and make key agents aware of its existence within your organisation.
- Include training information on HR communications and post-recruitment documentation.

Recommendation 3: Consider Obligatory Training – Traditionally, when any gender specific training is optional, attendance rate can be low. If possible, the training could be obligatory for new employees.

Recommendation 4: Engaging Men as Gender Equity Allies – Ensure male participants are targeted in the training. Engaging men as agents of change is critical to advancing gender equality. Men need to aware of their privileged position.

3.4 Action 4: **Conducting the training**

Recommendation 1: Verify if the workshop activities cover the following issues in all three areas of the workshop interest (1. Supporting skills development; 2. Deconstructing unconscious gender biases; 3. Becoming a leader):

- Supporting skills development – e.g.: effective, consistent and assertive communication as well as effective ability of publishing scientific contributions and attaining research funding, decision making, recognition of the situations of violating personal boundaries, discrimination and violence, reacting assertively and basing on the institutionally and legally available to those situations. Examples of workshops

could include 'How to write a research paper', 'Conference presentations skills training', 'Effective communication'.

- Deconstructing unconscious gender biases, e.g.: overview of inequality and unconscious bias, examine individual biases in groups and how to adjust them, explore the potential negative implications of not addressing unconscious bias, provide examples how individuals can address unconscious gender bias in decision making. Provide participants with a reading list, videos/podcast to explore the topic further.
- Becoming a leader, e.g.: The following topics could be included to assist in career progression: information on internal and external leadership programmes directed at women, CV development, project management, on successful female "different" leaders (role models: women being excellent leaders without complying with dominant culture and practices), barriers to change and how to overcome them. Deconstruct the male association with leadership and provide information on effective leadership behaviors and ways for women to increase self-confidence as a leader.

3.5 Action 5: **Training evaluation including both trainers and trainees' input**

Recommendation 1: A standard section (1-2 questions) in course evaluation to confirm gender sensitivity of the course should be prepared by the institution.

Recommendation 2: If possible, **orchestrate a follow up with participants**, for example networking event, lean in circles, zoom calls etc.

4. Recommendations for supporting caregivers in their careers

Action 1	Setting up a webpage dedicated to work-family balance
Action 2	Negotiation with the leadership for work-life balance measures (Parents' Travel Grant, revision of duties after parental leave is taken, acknowledgement of the time devoted to care)

4.1 Action 1: Setting up a webpage dedicated to work-family balance

Checklist:

- ✓ Have you collected national provisions/ policies on work-family balance?
- ✓ Have you verified the availability of work-family balance tools at your organisation (e.g. flexible working arrangement, parent-child room, nursery, additional health insurance, etc.)/
- ✓ Have you collected procedures (and documents/forms) necessary in the application processes? Or have you collected all necessary links to the description these procedures?
- ✓ In particular, have you provided accessible and comprehensible descriptions of maternity/paternity/family leave procedures, rights and obligations of employees being on a leave and the impact of leaves on career development? Or have you collected all necessary links to the description these procedures?
- ✓ Have you found work-family facilities as parent-child rooms, nurseries, kindergartens, sport centres, etc. at your organisation (e.g. on university campus)?
- ✓ Have you grouped available policies, tools and procedures into wider categories, e.g. childcare, elderly care, health issues, leisure time, etc?
- ✓ Have you collected contact information to all departments responsible for work-family measures?
- ✓ Have you decided where the webpage will be located (e.g. as a tab available from the organisational main page or as a subpage of an individual department/office)?
- ✓ Have you contacted the web page administrator?
- ✓ Did you take care of the graphic design of the website?

4.2 Action 2: Negotiation with the leadership for work-life balance measures

These negotiations should cover at least the following topics: Parents' Travel Grant, revision of duties after parental leave is taken, acknowledgement of the time devoted to care.

Recommendation 1. Know the issue

- ✓ You need to have a detailed grasp of the problem that the measure you are advocating for addresses. Be able to demonstrate relatively objective, reliable and verifiable evidence on the impact of caring responsibilities on academic careers of women, including their mobility, productivity and promotion (e.g. motherhood penalty). If available, use relevant data from your organisation.
- ✓ Analyse who the beneficiaries of the negotiated measure would be.
- ✓ Have a list of other research organisations/universities which had already introduced similar measures (best practices).
- ✓ Identify in what offices the relevant decisions are being made and, therefore, with whom to negotiate.

Recommendation 2 Articulate the gains (and harms)

- ✓ Point tangible benefits, the positive impacts that adoption of the proposed measure would have on the beneficiaries, all employees (including men) and the organisation as a whole, as well as to the negative impacts that would result from inaction.
- ✓ Identify possible opposing arguments and think of ways to counter-act them.
- ✓ Collect evidence on positive results of implementing advocated measures elsewhere

Recommendation 3. Connect the advocated measures to the organisational, national and/or international legal provisions and policies

- ✓ E.g. to the organisational mission, strategy, GEP
- ✓ E.g. to the EU Directive (2019/1158) on work-life balance for parents and carers, which recommends/ obliges that “workers who are parents and carers have the right to request flexible working arrangements for the purpose of adjusting their working patterns, including (...) through the use of remote working arrangements, flexible working schedules or a reduction in working hours, for the purposes of providing care”

Recommendation 4. Clarify your aim

- ✓ Consult the details of a solution with relevant stakeholders (people directly affected by the issue you are working on), e.g. which expenses could be covered by the Parents' Travel Grant fund, which duties could be reduced after returning from parental leave. Prepare a clear plan for the implementation of the advocated measure including timetable, responsibilities, resources needed, etc.
- ✓ Have at hand a second-best alternative for the measure (e.g. pilot programmes at few departments).

Recommendation 5. Build alliances

- ✓ To enhance your negotiation position, mobilise support of different stakeholders. In particular, the voices of those most affected by the measure that you want to introduce should be included (e.g. doctoral students, early career employees). Find allies among middle level management (including men). Engage in the negotiation and implementation processes gender structures and trade unions.

Recommendation 6. Communicate effectively

- ✓ The style of negotiation need not be antagonistic. Rather than reprimanding and blaming for failing to recognise the needs of employees and provide good working conditions, focus on how to improve working conditions and the effectiveness of the organisation as a whole.
- ✓ Know your messages well and how to support them with the evidence you have gathered. Messages should be clear, consistent, and ideally succinct.
- ✓ Report your negotiation attempts and results to organisational stakeholders, including doctoral students (if applicable), early career employees and trade unions. Adjust your messaging to the needs and interests of the different audiences.

Recommendation 7. Embed measures

- ✓ Strive for embedding the implemented measures in the organizational agenda and structure.

Recommendation 8. Monitor implementation of measures

- ✓ Make sure the negotiated measures and benefits are communicated to all employees on a regular basis.
- ✓ Regularly monitor the implementation of the measures, and their effectiveness - think forward to what can be improved in the future.

5. Recommendations for increasing gender awareness and breaking down stereotypes

Action 1	Needs analysis in the area of breaking down gender stereotypes in research and academia
Action 2	Preparation of training (for woman and men in top management positions) composed of 3 modules: : (1) Evidence on gender gaps; (2) Deconstructing Unconscious Gender Biases; (3) Gendering Research
Action 3	Promotion and recruitment of the training
Action 4	Conducting the training
Action 5	Training evaluation including both trainers and trainees input

5.1 Action 1: Needs analysis in the area of breaking down gender stereotypes in research and academia

Recommendation 1 Define the goals of the training

Recommendation 2 Identify expected change achieved by the training

Recommendation 3 Identify the areas where the action is most needed

Recommendation 4. Identify processes and procedures which support the foreseen change

Recommendation 5 Identify potential organizational challenges and resistance among staff

5.2 Action 2: Preparation of training (for woman and men in top management positions) composed of 3 modules: (1) Evidence on gender gaps; (2) Deconstructing Unconscious Gender Biases; (3) Gendering Research

Recommendation 1 Ensure standards by choosing adequate methodology

Recommendation 2 Ensure standards by preparing high quality content and materials

Recommendation 3 Ensure standards by choosing professional equality trainer. Due to the fact that the workshop is intended for senior researchers and professors in top-management positions please consider hiring external trainers to avoid professional dependences.

5.3 Action 3: Promotion and recruitment of the training

Recommendation 1 Encourage people to attend the training

- ✓ **Develop a system of recognition and incentives such as attendance certificates, credits, or badges.**
- ✓ **Ensure support from top management.**
- ✓ **Suggest managers/supervisors to select employees to attend.**
- ✓ **Emphasise the legal obligation of civil servants to promote gender equality.**

5.4 Action 4: Conducting the training

Recommendation 1 Ensure the workshop:

- ✓ provides facts, figures and indicators on the social and economic situation of men and women in your institution;
- ✓ supports self-reflection and self-awareness,
- ✓ helps to define personal and social identity;
- ✓ helps to understand the origin and functioning of gender stereotypes;
- ✓ creates anti-discriminatory attitudes and behaviours;
- ✓ presents gender equality in a comprehensive legal context;
- ✓ helps to incorporate gender-linked considerations and perspectives;
- ✓ illustrates the wide and diverse context of gender equality.

5.5 Action 5: Training evaluation including both trainers and trainees' input

Recommendation 1 Verify, accordingly to the set objectives, if a desired outcomes had been achieved.

Recommendation 2 Compare trainers' and trainees' perspectives.

References & further reading

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EIGE toolkit on Gender Equality in Academia and Research: <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear/integration-gender-dimension-research-and-teaching-content>

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Quality Standards Concerning the Content of Gender Equality Training Acting Pro(e)quality Quality Standards for Gender Equality and Diversity Training in the EU Pro(E)quality EQUAL Transnational Cooperation, 2007 Available in EIGE’s database at: <http://www.eige.europa.eu>

Resources and Links

Festa Project/ Supera project	Handbook on resistance to Gender equality in Academia based on recommendations from the Festa project.	Handbook	https://www.superaproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/HANDBOOK-ON-RESISTANCE-TO-GENDER-EQUALITY.pdf
Festa project	An array of resources available on this website to assist with training content, delivery, and encouraging participation.	Website	http://resge.eu/?Page=Analysis&Back=40
LERU	Paper on implicit bias – examines mechanisms behind loss of female talent in academia.	Advice Paper	https://www.leru.org/files/implicit-bias-in-academia-full-paper.pdf
Supera project	Overview of training methodology	PDF	https://www.superaproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/Lotus-Blossom.pdf
Supera project	This webinar, designed for RFOs, will illuminate	Webinar	https://www.superaproject.eu/event/webinar-4/

	how RFOs can intervene to avoid unconscious biases in their work		
ACT on Gender	<p>Toolkit for the Communities of Practice (CoP) of the ACT project their Facilitators. It also shows how and with the use of which tools and methods the toolkit can help CoPs operate, develop, implement gender equality plans (GEP), gender equality (GE) measures and activities, and facilitate institutional change in relation to GE in HE and R&I</p>	Handbook	<p>https://www.genderportal.eu/resources/act-co-creation-toolkit-version-20-complete</p>

EIGE	Resources on the Integration of the sex/gender dimension into research and teaching content	Toolkit	https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear/integration-gender-dimension-research-and-teaching-content
EIGE	Gender equality in academia research	Toolkit	https://eige.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/mh0716096enn_1.pdf